

A Method for Estimation of Elementary Constituents in Coal

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The knowledge of elemental analysis of coal has got great significance from the point of view of its classification and industrial use. A number of methods¹ are available for estimating the elements but not a single method can estimate all the four constituents, viz. C, H, S and N at a time in a single experiment.

The present communication reports the development of an inexpensive method to determine all major elements like carbon, hydrogen, sulphur and nitrogen at a time in a single experiment within a very short time without using costly sophisticated instrument.

Results and Discussion

Using different standard organic samples and coals of different fields/ranks as samples for experiments and following the experimental procedure as discussed later, calibration curves were drawn by plotting corresponding increase in weight per gram of dry sample due to absorption of carbon dioxide, water, oxides of sulphur and oxides of nitrogen. Four formulas have been developed from these curves for estimating directly percent carbon, hydrogen, sulphur and nitrogen on dry basis: for carbon, $C = 27.8 X_1$; for hydrogen, $H = 11.2 X_2$; for sulphur, $S = 66.3 X_3$ and for nitrogen, $N = 234 X_4$, where C, H, S and N stand for percent carbon, hydrogen, sulphur and nitrogen respectively on dry basis, and X_1 , X_2 , X_3 and X_4 for corresponding increase in weight per gram of dry sample due to absorption of oxides of carbon, hydrogen, sulphur and nitrogen respectively. Arbitrary constants were computed from the curves.

Different unknown samples were analysed both by conventional Indian Standard Method and by the proposed method. By using the formulae the percents for C, H, S and N on dry basis were calculated. The results (Table 1) as obtained by this method are in consonance with those obtained by Indian Standard Method. The proposed method has the same repeatability as in Indian Standard Method.

The apparatus (Fig. 1) and the method as developed is very simple, quick and inexpensive. This single-experiment method eliminates the several steps and time-consumable procedure for separate estimation of the C, H, S and N by the conventional method. For routine analysis four determinations in one working day can easily be done.

Experimental

The assembly of apparatus is described in Fig. 1. It consists of at one end a set of purifying train to purify oxygen for combustion, then comes combustion tube placed inside

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COAL SAMPLES*

Sample, location	Moisture %	Ash %	C %	H %	S %	N %
Raniganj, W.B.	8.4	37.5	43.50 (43.72)	4.11 4.03	1.00 1.02	0.83 0.95
Talcher, Orissa	12.6	15.9	63.52 (63.58)	5.90 5.81	0.88 0.64	1.61 1.56
Mirzapur, U.P.	6.6	26.2	57.24 (57.24)	4.50 4.52	1.00 1.05	1.24 1.20
Hardagadh, U.P.	1.8	24.4	62.10 (62.19)	4.50 4.43	0.50 0.51	1.46 1.40
Tartaric acid	—	—	31.97 (32.01)	4.00 4.03	0 0	0 0
Jayant, Turra Sean, M.P.	11.1	14.4 (66.40)	66.81 6.07	6.14 0.53	0.53 1.45	1.40
Kalimela, Janadoba, Bihar	1.2	28.4	57.71 (57.72)	3.95 3.98	0.81 0.82	1.40 1.49
Gurghella Seam, M.P.	9.7	9.0	74.10 (73.89)	6.23 6.18	0.80 0.61	1.71 1.76
Lignite	8.8	29.7	42.34 (42.13)	4.85 4.73	8.56 8.60	0.70 0.71
Sucrose	—	—	41.86 (42.11)	6.41 6.48	0 0	0 0
Coal, M.P.	8.4	32.2	50.58 (50.58)	4.53 4.52	0.60 0.57	1.10 1.07
Golakdih ROM, Jharia, Bihar	0.7	36.2	54.62 (54.37)	3.23 3.27	0.35 0.32	1.40 1.35
Renusagar, U.P.	2.3	28.2	58.10 (58.36)	4.12 4.22	0.59 0.47	1.26 1.26
Karanpura	3.4	48.8	36.00 (36.06)	2.98 3.06	0.39 0.39	0.75 0.73
Amlorhi, M.P.	5.0	30.2	52.87 (52.97)	4.19 4.28	0.68 0.53	1.19 1.11
Samla, W.B.	5.6	13.2	66.81 (66.81)	5.31 5.47	0.44 0.41	2.05 1.99
Margherita, Assam	1.8	3.0	79.42 (79.01)	5.60 5.61	2.02 2.18	1.10 1.09
Treated Niljai coal, Wardha	4.6	26.8	53.85 (53.74)	4.46 4.42	1.67 1.77	1.24 1.29
Ramkanali, Jharia, Bihar	0.9	26.3	63.70 (63.97)	3.51 3.53	0.35 0.31	1.33 1.34
Treated coal with anthracene	14.4	4.8	88.91 (88.89)	6.26 6.36	1.62 1.51	2.11 2.09
Renusagar, U.P.	2.6	26.9	60.52 (60.78)	4.33 4.34	0.84 0.74	1.31 1.32

*Figure in parenthesis obtained by Indian Standard Method on dry basis.

two furnaces—Furnace no.1 to be maintained at 800° and Furnace no. 2 initially to be kept at 650° and then finally to be raised to 800°. At the other end, there is absorption train : absorption tube no. 1 (containing fused lead

series (Fig. 1) and the sample (0.10–0.15 g), size 211 micron) taken in a silica boat was transferred quickly in combustion tube and pushed it very slowly in the hottest zone so that time taken to reach the hottest zone was 25

Fig 1 Assembly of apparatus.

chromate for absorption of oxides of sulphur) to be kept inside Furnace no. 3 maintaining temperature at 300°, absorption tube no. 2 (packed with silver gauge to remove halides, if any) to be placed inside Furnace no. 4 maintaining temperature at 120°, absorption tube no. 3 (containing magnesium perchlorate for absorption of water), absorption tube no. 4 (containing specially prepared reagent for absorption of oxides of nitrogen), absorption tube no. 5 (containing soda asbestos for absorption of carbon dioxide) and absorption tube no. 6 (containing soda asbestos and magnesium perchlorate for absorption of carbon dioxide, if any, and water), and a bubbler to note the flow of gas.

Magnesium perchlorate (16–22 mesh, B.D.H.), soda asbestos (6–12 mesh, B.D.H.), fused lead chromate (prepared by fusing B.D.H. make lead chromate at 800° and broken into 6–12 mesh size), silver gauge (40 mesh, B.D.H.), and specially prepared reagent by adding a solution of potassium dichromate in sulphuric acid to silicon dioxide (-52 + 72 BS size) followed by shaking.

Procedure : At first, the temperature of Furnace nos. 1, 2, 3 and 4 were raised to 800, 650, 300 and 120° respectively. Initially weighed absorption tubes were attached in

min. The boat was kept here for further 15 min. Meanwhile, temperature of the second furnace was raised from 650 to 800°. Then the absorption tubes were detached, cooled and weighed, and the increase in weights calculated.

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References

1. A. R. PANICKER and N. G. BANERJEE, *Analyst*, 1958, 83, 296; S. N. MUKHERJEE, P. DUTTA and P. B. DUTTA, *Indian J. Tech.*, 1968, 31, N. S. SHIMP, *Energy Sources*, 1977, 3, 93; ASTM-D3177-84, ASTM-D1757-86, IS 1351-1959; N. S. RAWAT, *Chem. Ind.*, 1976, 17, 743; P. MOHRNAUR, *Gas Wasserfach*, 1968, 21, 561; IS 1350-1959; L. J. DARLAGE and S. S. BLOCK, *J. Chromatogr. Sci.*, 1973, 12, 1272; A. W. HAI, *US Bureau of Mines Rep. Invest.*, 1975, 8038, 12; B. B. SINHA and S. MAHARAJ, *Fuel Sci. Technol.*, 1993, 12, 53; IS 1350 (P-IV Sec-1), 1974; S. R. SINGH, B. B. SINHA and S. B. CHATTOPADHYAY, *Fuel Sci. Technol.*, 1989, 8, 47; N. G. BANERJEE, *J. Sci. Ind. Res., Sect. B*, 1953, 12, 24; ASTM D4239-85